

РАЗДЕЛ. ТЕХНИЧЕСКИЕ НАУКИ

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20260805>

UDK 665.77

**STUDY OF THE CONDITIONS FOR PRODUCING
BITUMEN BASED ON ALTERNATIVE FEEDSTOCKS
AND OXIDIZING AGENTS**

Atayev Matlab Shichbala,

Associate Professor, Petrochemical technology and industrial ecology
Department.,

Mirzali Elvin Sardar,

Master's student,
Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University (ASOIU)

Annotation: This study presents a technological assessment of producing road petroleum bitumen from alternative hydrocarbon feedstock derived from waste tire pyrolysis. The heavy fraction of tire pyrolysis oil (boiling above 290 °C) was evaluated as a potential substitute for conventional petroleum vacuum residue in air oxidation processes. The influence of pyrolysis reactor type and operating temperature on product distribution was analyzed, and the advantages of a rotary kiln reactor for industrial-scale processing were substantiated. Fractionation characteristics, elemental composition, H/C ratio, density, and aromaticity of the heavy fraction were examined to determine its suitability for structured oxidation. Based on industrial analogues of serpentine tube oxidation units, optimal process parameters, including temperature range, air pressure, recirculation ratio, and residence time, were proposed for controlled oxidation of the heavy pyrolysis fraction. The suggested technological regime enables the production of road petroleum bitumen grade NYB 60-90 (equivalent to BND 60/90 according to GOST 22245-90) with penetration values within the standard range. The results demonstrate that tire-derived heavy pyrolysis fractions represent a technologically feasible and resource-efficient alternative feedstock for bitumen production.

Keywords: alternative feedstock, waste tire pyrolysis, rotary kiln reactor, heavy pyrolysis fraction, air oxidation, oxidized bitumen, road bitumen

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ УСЛОВИЙ ПРОИЗВОДСТВА БИТУМА НА ОСНОВЕ АЛЬТЕРНАТИВНОГО СЫРЬЯ И ОКИСЛЯЮЩИХ АГЕНТОВ

Атаев Матлаб Шичбала,
доц., кафедры нефтехимической технологии и промышленной
экологии,
Мирзали Эльвин Сардар,
магистрант,
Азербайджанский государственный нефтегазовый университет
(АНОИУ),

Аннотация: В данном исследовании представлена технологическая оценка производства дорожного нефтяного битума из альтернативного углеводородного сырья, получаемого путем пиролиза отработанных шин. Тяжелая фракция пиролизного масла из шин (кипящая температура выше 290 °С) была оценена как потенциальная замена традиционному вакуумному остатку нефти в процессах окисления воздухом. Проанализировано влияние типа пиролизного реактора и рабочей температуры на распределение продуктов, а также обоснованы преимущества вращающегося печного реактора для промышленной переработки. Для определения пригодности тяжелой фракции к структурированному окислению изучены характеристики фракционирования, элементный состав, соотношение Н/С, плотность и ароматичность. На основе промышленных аналогов змеевидных трубчатых установок окисления предложены оптимальные параметры процесса, включая температурный диапазон, давление воздуха, коэффициент рециркуляции и время пребывания, для контролируемого окисления тяжелой пиролизной фракции. Предложенный технологический режим позволяет производить дорожный нефтяной битум марки NYB 60-90 (эквивалентный BND 60/90 по ГОСТ 22245-90) со значениями

пенетрации в пределах стандартного диапазона. Результаты показывают, что тяжелые пиролизные фракции, полученные из шин, представляют собой технологически осуществимую и ресурсоэффективную альтернативу сырью для производства битума.

Ключевые слова: альтернативное сырье, пиролиз отработанных шин, вращающийся реактор, тяжелая пиролизная фракция, окисление воздухом, окисленный битум, дорожный битум

Introduction. The development of road transport and construction infrastructure in our country has led to an increased demand for bitumen and bitumen-based materials. Currently, this demand is mainly satisfied by heavy residues obtained in the petroleum refining industry. However, the limitation of the raw material base, variability in the quality of heavy residues, and high energy consumption necessitate the improvement of bitumen production processes. In this regard, the involvement of alternative raw material sources and the adaptation of existing technologies to new types of feedstock are of significant scientific and technological importance. The study of the potential use of heavy fractions of pyrolysis oils obtained from the pyrolysis of waste automobile tires in bitumen production is one of the relevant issues [1-4]. Due to their high aromaticity and low hydrogen-to-carbon ratio, these fractions exhibit behavior similar to conventional petroleum-derived vacuum residue and semi-residue during the oxidation process, significantly influencing the process conditions, intensity, and the quality of the final product. In oxidation processes applied in bitumen production, the chemical composition of the feedstock, temperature, and reaction time play a key role [2-6]. When using alternative raw materials, optimization of these parameters becomes necessary. Therefore, the study of the conditions for producing bitumen based on alternative feedstock and oxidizing agents, as well as the assessment of the industrial applicability of these processes, represents a relevant scientific and technical task.

Problem Statement. The gradual depletion of conventional petroleum-derived heavy feedstock resources used in the production of road and construction bitumen, as well as the instability of their quality indicators, necessitates the involvement of alternative raw material sources. Approximately 2.5 billion tires are produced annually worldwide, and a

comparable volume of waste tires is generated each year (Market Reports World, 2026). In this context, the use of heavy hydrocarbon fractions obtained from the pyrolysis of waste automobile tires in bitumen production is of both current relevance and practical importance. A systematic evaluation of the behavior of alternative feedstock in the production process of oxidized bitumen, the determination of optimal process conditions, and the assurance of compliance of the resulting bitumen with standard specifications constitute important technological and scientific challenges. The study of the influence of parameters such as reactor temperature, type and concentration of the oxidizing medium, and process duration on the physical and mechanical properties of bitumen is crucial from the standpoint of industrial design and application. The main objectives of this research are as follows: to analyze the potential of heavy fractions obtained from tire pyrolysis as alternative feedstock for bitumen production; to comparatively evaluate the effect of oxidation conditions on bitumen quality; and, based on the obtained results, to determine the prospects for industrial application of the proposed process.

Methods of Solution. Tires are mainly composed of high-molecular-weight hydrocarbons, polymeric materials containing aromatic and naphthenic structures, carbon black, and sulfur-containing compounds. As a result of the thermal pyrolysis process, these components decompose, leading to the formation of liquid fractions characterized by high carbon content, high aromaticity, and a relatively low H/C ratio. These characteristics are close to the chemical nature of conventional heavy petroleum residues (vacuum residue and semi-residue) used for the production of oxidized bitumen. For this reason, heavy fractions obtained from tire pyrolysis are considered promising alternative feedstocks in oxidation processes in terms of structural development and viscosity increase.

Table 1 – Typical composition of passenger car and truck tires (Evans et al., 2006)

Component	Passenger Car Tire (%)	Truck Tire (%)
Rubber	47	45
Carbon black	21.5	22
Metal	16.5	21.5

Component	Passenger Car Tire (%)	Truck Tire (%)
Textile	5.5	–
Zinc oxide	1	2
Sulfur	1	1
Additives	7.5	5

The rubber fraction consists of Natural Rubber (NR – cis-1,4-polyisoprene), Styrene-Butadiene Rubber (SBR), and Butadiene Rubber (BR). In bitumen production, the initial stage of tire processing involves subjecting the tire material to pyrolysis with the aim of maximizing the yield of pyrolysis oil.

Pyrolysis Process. In a study conducted by Aydın and İlkılıç (2012), the pyrolysis of waste automobile tires was investigated in a fixed-bed, batch-type reactor. The process was carried out within a temperature range of 400-700 °C, and the optimal product distribution was achieved at approximately 500 °C. Under these conditions, the mass distribution of pyrolysis products was as follows: liquid fraction (pyrolysis oil) – 40.26 wt.%, solid residue (carbonized material) – 47.88 wt.%, and gaseous products – 11.86 wt.%. The obtained results indicate that although increasing the temperature in fixed-bed reactors promotes the formation of liquid products, heat transfer is limited due to the immobility of the feedstock within the reactor, resulting in a relatively high yield of solid residue. This characteristic demonstrates that fixed-bed reactors are more suitable for laboratory and industrial-scale studies, whereas reactor types that provide continuous and more homogeneous processing are preferable under industrial conditions.

The following parameters represent the optimal operating conditions proposed for an industrial-scale rotary kiln reactor designed for the processing of 30 tons of waste tires per day.

Table 2 – Proposed Optimal Operating Parameters for a contemporary Rotary Kiln Reactor

Parameter	Value
Temperature	430–480 °C
Rotational speed	0.45 rpm
Residence time	55 min

Parameter	Value
Heating rate	10 °C/min
Oxygen concentration	0.5 %
Tire particle size	3–4 cm
Moisture content	1 %
Reactor filling degree	15 %

Table 3 – Expected Product Distribution at 450 °C

Product	Yield (%)
Pyrolysis oil	47 %
Carbon black (char)	33 %
Gas fraction	11 %
Steel	9 %

Figure 1 – Effect of reaction temperature on the yield of pyrolysis products

Yazdani et al. (2019) conducted the pyrolysis of waste tires in a laboratory-scale rotary furnace reactor made of quartz, electrically heated and rotating at a speed of 1 rpm. The process was carried out at seven different temperatures within the range of 400–1050 °C under a nitrogen inert atmosphere with a flow rate of 70 cm³/min. The heating regime

consisted of two stages: temperature ramping (20-30 min) and isothermal holding (total duration 120 min). The study determined that the optimal pyrolysis temperature for the rotary furnace was 550 °C, at which maximum yields of 44 wt.% pyrolysis oil, 21.7% gas, and 34.5% char were obtained. Increasing the temperature above 550 °C accelerated secondary cracking reactions, leading to the conversion of liquid products into gas and a decrease in oil yield.

Figure 1 – Schematic of the Rotary Kiln reactor

(1 – Nitrogen cylinder; 2 – Flow controller; 3 – Rotary Kiln reactor; 4 – Furnace; 5 – Heat exchanger; 6 – Separator; 7 – Pyrolysis oil tank; I – Nitrogen; II – Pyrolysis products (excluding coke and metals); III– Gases; IV – Pyrolysis oil)

The composition of the obtained pyrolysis oil was analyzed by FT-IR and distillation analyses. The oil was found to consist mainly of alkanes and aromatic compounds and to contain 46% of a heavy fraction corresponding to VGO (Vacuum Gas Oil, >350 °C). Although laboratory studies often determine the optimal pyrolysis temperature as 500-550°C, industrial rotary kiln reactors operate more efficiently within the 430-480°C range. In large-scale systems, heat transfer limitations, larger particle beds, and non-uniform temperature distribution increase the risk of secondary cracking at higher temperatures. Operation above 500°C promotes excessive gas formation, reduces liquid yield, and increases energy consumption and thermal stress on reactor materials. Therefore, the 430–480°C range ensures stable heat transfer, minimizes secondary

reactions, improves energy efficiency, and provides optimal heavy fraction quality under continuous industrial conditions.

Figure 2 – Dependence of pyrolysis oil yield on temperature

Table 4 – Elemental analysis of the obtained products

Element	Test Method	Liquid (wt %.)	Solid (wt %.)	Gas (wt %.)
Carbon	ASTM D5291	87.00	77.80	87.35
Hydrogen	ASTM D5291	11.10	0.65	11.14
Nitrogen	ASTM D5291	<0.5	<0.1	–
Sulfur	ASTM D4294	0.85	2.08	0.31

It was determined that with increasing temperature, the yield of solid residue (char) decreases, while the amount of gaseous products increases, and the maximum yield of the liquid fraction (pyrolysis oil) is obtained within the intermediate temperature range. Due to the movement of tire particles inside the rotary kiln reactor, the pyrolysis process acquired a more homogeneous character, preventing local overheating of the feedstock and increasing the proportion of aromatic and unsaturated hydrocarbons in the liquid product composition.

The selection of reactor type for the pyrolysis of waste automobile tires directly affects process efficiency and the quality of the obtained

products. Among various reactor types, rotary kiln reactors are considered more suitable for processing heterogeneous and mechanically complex feedstock. In such reactors, the rubber, metal cord, and textile components of tires continuously advance under the influence of gravity and rotational motion, thereby preventing hydrodynamic complications. In rotary kiln reactors, heat transfer occurs mainly through wall contact and radiation, ensuring uniform heating of large particles, while continuous mixing reduces the risk of local coking. Structural simplicity, low probability of clogging, and suitability for continuous industrial operation justify the technological and economic advantages of this reactor type for waste tire pyrolysis.

Table 5 – Chemical composition of the gas released during the pyrolysis process (average, vol.%)

Component	% (Vol.)
Methane	32.92
Hydrogen	21.11
Ethane	13.05
Carbon dioxide	12.06
Carbon monoxide	6.41
Propane	5.15
Propene	3.76
Ethylene	1.94
1-Butene	1.25
2-Fumaric acid	1.27
Butane	0.91
Nitrogen	0.86
Isobutane	0.30
Cis-2-butene	0.08
Pentane	0.06
Hydrogen chloride	<0.01
Hydrogen sulfide	<3 (mg/m ³)

Fractionation of Pyrolysis Oil

The fractionation of tire pyrolysis oil (TPO) was carried out at a maximum boiling temperature of 290 °C without applying reflux. The feed was introduced into the column at room temperature without preheating, and the feed flow rate was maintained constant at 20 kg/h. The selection of a reflux ratio of 0 caused the separation process to proceed mainly according to a simple evaporation–condensation mechanism. The temperature distribution along the column exhibited a weak gradient. While the temperature in the reboiler was 290 °C, the temperature at the top of the column was 160 °C. Within the T4-T10 intervals, the temperature varied between 160-214 °C. The relatively small temperature difference between the top and bottom sections (particularly only a few degrees in the rectification zone) indicates reduced separation selectivity due to the absence of reflux. Under these conditions, a broader range of hydrocarbons can pass into the light fraction.

In terms of fraction yields, under high boiling temperature conditions, the light fraction (LF) yield was approximately 36.7%, while the heavy fraction (HF) accounted for 63.3%. Increasing the temperature intensified evaporation, leading to near-maximal separation of light components. The light fraction was dominated by aromatic compounds. Toluene (11.8%), (p+m)-xylene (9.8%), benzene (4.5%), ethylbenzene (3.5%), and limonene (4.9%) were identified as the main components. The total BTEX content was 34.3%, indicating a high concentration of aromatic hydrocarbons. The heavy fraction was characterized by more aromatized and condensed structures. According to elemental analysis, it contained 87.9% carbon, 9.1% hydrogen, 0.8% nitrogen, and 1.3% sulfur. An H/C ratio of 1.2 indicates a high degree of aromaticity. The lower heating value of the heavy fraction was 41.8 MJ/kg, and its density at 20 °C was 1.04 g/mL. The water content was 191 ppm, flash point 72 °C, pH 5.7, and total acidity 9.48 mgKOH/g. The BTEX content in this fraction was only 0.5%, while limonene accounted for 0.9%, indicating that light aromatics were almost completely transferred to the light fraction.

Thus, fractionation at 290 °C without reflux ensured effective separation of light aromatics, while the heavy fraction exhibited an increased concentration of higher molecular weight and more aromatized components. These characteristics demonstrate the suitability of the heavy

fraction as a potential feedstock for subsequent oxidation processes or the production of bitumen-like materials.

Figure 2 – Distillation process of TPO

(1 – TPO storage tank; 2 – Secondary TPO storage tank; 3 – Pump; 4 – Distillation column; 5 – Reboiler; 6 – Heavy fraction tank; 7 – Condensation column; 8 – Light fraction tank; 9 – Light fraction tank; I – Tire pyrolysis oil; II – Light fraction; III – Heavy fraction; IV – Cooled LF; V – Water; VI – Cooled LF; VIII – Gases; IX – C1 – C4 gases)

Table 6 – Products of the distillation process

Parameter	290 °C, No Reflux HF	290 °C, No Reflux LF
Carbon (wt.%)	87.9	87.9
Hydrogen (wt.%)	9.1	11.1
Nitrogen (wt.%)	0.8	0.3
Sulfur (wt.%)	1.3	0.7
H/C ratio	1.2	1.5
Higher Heating Value (HHV,	41.8	41.0

Parameter	290 °C, No Reflux HF	290 °C, No Reflux LF
MJ/kg)		
Density (at 20 °C, g/mL)	1.04	0.88
Water Content (ppm)	191	127
Flash Point (°C)	72	<25
pH	5.7	6.5
Total Acid Number (TAN, mgKOH/g)	–	–
Limonene (wt.%)	0.9	4.9
Benzene (wt.%)	0.0	4.5
Toluene (wt.%)	0.1	11.8
Ethylbenzene (wt.%)	0.1	3.5
(p + m)-Xylene (wt.%)	0.1	9.8
o-Xylene + Styrene (wt.%)	0.2	4.7
Total BTEX (wt.%)	0.5	34.3

Oxidation of the Heavy Fraction

In bitumen production units equipped with serpentine tube reactors, petroleum bitumen is obtained as a result of the oxidation process. As feedstock, gudron, semi-gudron, and residues of heavy oils boiling above 350 °C are used. The main products of the unit are road, construction, roofing, and special viscous bitumens. The yield of viscous road bitumen is approximately 98 wt.%, while the yield of construction bitumen is 94-96 wt.%. According to the technological regime, the feedstock is heated to 260-270 °C in the serpentine tubes of the furnace and then introduced into the reactor. In the reactor, the temperature is maintained within the range of 270-275 °C as a result of oxidation. The reaction products are at a temperature of 170-200 °C in the evaporator. Commercial bitumen is obtained at the outlet of the cooler within the temperature range of 180-220 °C. The recirculation ratio (by mass) is 3:1-8:1. The compressed air pressure is 0.7-0.8 MPa, the pressure at the reactor inlet is 0.6-0.7 MPa, and in the evaporator it is 0.15-0.20 MPa. The suitability of this unit for the heavy fraction of tire pyrolysis is determined by its operating principle. The tire-derived heavy fraction is rich in aromaticity and resinous components, which create properties close to those of gudron. During oxidation,

molecular weight increases and structural densification occurs; therefore, under appropriate temperature and recirculation conditions, this fraction can be oxidized and considered a technologically promising feedstock for obtaining a bitumen-type product.

Table 7 – Proposed parameters of the oxidation process

Indicator	Proposed Range for Heavy Pyrolysis Fraction (290 °C)
Temperature of feed leaving the furnace, °C	235–245
Temperature of product leaving the reactor, °C	245–255
Bitumen temperature after the cooler, °C	160–190
Commercial bitumen temperature (cooler outlet), °C	170–200
Recirculation ratio (by mass)	(1.5–3) : 1
Compressed air pressure, MPa	0.6–0.7
Pressure at reactor inlet, MPa	0.12–0.18
Pressure in the evaporator, MPa	0.10–0.15
Reaction time (residence time), min	10–15
Linear velocity in reactor tubes, m/s	4–6
Vapor velocity (in evaporator), m/s	≤ 0.10
Vapor velocity (in separator), m/s	≤ 0.25
Specific volume of reaction zone, m ³ /(t·h)	0.2–0.6
Residual oxygen content in bitumen, wt. %	0.5–2.0

Figure 3 – Technological scheme of bitumen production in a serpentine tube reactor (oxidation of feedstock in foamed state)
 (1, 4, 9, 12, 15 – Pumps; 2 – Receiving tank; 3 – Furnace; 5 – Mixer; 6 – Air receiver-Reactor; 8 – Compressor; 10 – Evaporator; 11, 14 – Air coolers; 13 – Separator; 16 – Furnace; I – Heavy pyrolysis fraction; II – Air; III – Heavy fuel oil; IV – Bitumen; V – Gases; VI – Fuel)

The proposed technological regime ensures structural hardening through controlled oxidation of the heavy pyrolysis fraction, resulting in the production of road bitumen grade NYB 60–90 (equivalent to BND 60/90 according to GOST 22245-90). In the process, the feedstock outlet temperature from the furnace is maintained at 235–245 °C, while the reactor outlet temperature is kept within 245–255 °C. This prevents excessive coking of the fraction and ensures stable progression of oxidation reactions. The selection of a recirculation ratio within the range of 1.5–3:1 ensures the return of partially oxidized, more viscous product to the reaction zone, thereby promoting gradual hardening of the molecular structure. A residence time of 10–15 minutes and a linear velocity of 4–6 m/s in the reactor tubes ensure homogeneous distribution of oxygen in the liquid phase. Supplying compressed air at a pressure of 0.6–0.7 MPa accelerates the reaction kinetics, while maintaining the reactor inlet pressure at 0.12–0.18 MPa prevents excessive thermal cracking. Low vapor velocities in the evaporator and separator zones (≤ 0.25 m/s) ensure the removal of light components and increase the softening temperature of the residual product. The specific reaction zone volume is selected within 0.2–0.6 m³/(t·h), providing an optimal balance between oxidation depth and productivity. As a result, 0.5–2.0 wt.% residual oxygen is incorporated into the bitumen, leading to an increase in

asphaltene content and strengthening of the colloidal system. Thus, the combination of the indicated temperature, pressure, recirculation, and hydrodynamic parameters ensures structured oxidation of the heavy pyrolysis fraction and technologically substantiates the production of heat-resistant road bitumen grade NYB 60-90 with penetration in the range of 60-90.

Figure 3 – Graph of penetration versus reaction time

Figure 4 – Dependence of penetration on temperature (constant time)

Table 8 – Oxidation process products

Product	Yield, % (wt.)
Bitumen (NYB 60–90)	85–89
Heavy fuel oil	5–7
Gases and water vapor	4–6
Mechanical losses	≤ 1
Total	100

Conclusion. The conducted technological assessment demonstrates that the heavy fraction of tire pyrolysis oil (boiling above 290 °C) possesses physicochemical characteristics comparable to conventional petroleum vacuum residue and can therefore be considered a promising alternative feedstock for oxidized bitumen production. Its high carbon content, relatively low H/C ratio, elevated density, and pronounced aromaticity favor structural condensation reactions during air oxidation and promote the formation of a stable colloidal system. The analysis of pyrolysis conditions confirmed that rotary kiln reactors operating within the temperature range of 430–480 °C provide optimal product distribution and improved heavy fraction quality under industrial-scale processing. Fractionation without reflux at 290 °C enables effective separation of light aromatic components and concentration of high-molecular-weight structures in the heavy fraction, enhancing its suitability for subsequent oxidation. The suggested technological conditions ensure gradual structural hardening while preventing excessive thermal cracking and coking. Under these parameters, road petroleum bitumen grade NYB 60–90 (equivalent to BND 60/90 according to GOST 22245–90) can be obtained with penetration values within the required standard range. Overall, the results confirm the technological feasibility and resource efficiency of utilizing tire-derived heavy pyrolysis fractions in bitumen production, contributing to both waste valorization and diversification of the raw material base in the petroleum refining industry.

Bibliography

- [1] Mirzəyev R.Ş. Ağır neft qalıqlarının təkrar emalı. / R.Ş. Mirzəyev – Bakı, Azərbaycan: 2006, 187s.
- [2] Acevedo B. “Pyrolysis of blends of coal and tyre wastes in a fixed bed reactor and a rotary oven,” / B. Acevedo, C. Barriocanal, R. Alvarez // Fuel – 2013. Vol. 113. 817-825 p.
- [3] Yazdani P. “Study of waste tire pyrolysis in a rotary kiln reactor in a wide range of pyrolysis temperature” / P. Yazdani, P. Mellin, M. Ersson // Fuel – 2019. Vol. 236. 1590-1602 p.
- [4] Williams P.T. “End-of-life tyre conversion to energy: A review on pyrolysis and activated carbon production processes and their challenges” / P.T. Williams // Energy – 2013. Vol. 53. 1-21 p.
- [5] Hunter P. The Shell Bitumen Handbook / P. Hunter, A. Self, J. Read // 7th ed. – London, U.K.: ICE Publishing, 2023.
- [6] Zerín N.H. “End-of-life tyre conversion to energy: A review on pyrolysis and activated carbon production processes and their challenges” / N.H. Zerín, M.G. Rasul, M.I. Jahirul, A.S. M. Sayem // Science of the Total Environment – 2023. Vol. 905. 166981 p.

Список литературы (перевод)

- [1] Мирзаев Р.Ш. Переработка остатков тяжелой нефти. / Р.Ш. Мирзаев – Баку, Азербайджан: 2006, 187 с.
- [2] Асеведо Б. «Пиролиз смесей угля и отходов шин в реакторе с неподвижным слоем и вращающейся печи», / Б. Асеведо, К. Барриоканал, Р. Альварес // Топливо – 2013. Том 113. С. 817-825.
- [3] Яздани П. «Исследование пиролиза отходов шин в вращающемся печном реакторе в широком диапазоне температур пиролиза», / П. Яздани, П. Меллин, М. Эрссон // Топливо – 2019. Том 236. С. 1590-1602.
- [4] Уильямс П.Т. «Преобразование отработанных шин в энергию: обзор процессов пиролиза и производства активированного угля и связанных с ними проблем» / П.Т. Уильямс // Энергетика – 2013. Том 53. 1-21 с.
- [5] Хантер П. Справочник по битуму Shell / П. Хантер, А. Селф, Дж. Рид // 7-е изд. – Лондон, Великобритания: ICE Publishing, 2023.

[6] Зерин Н.Х. «Преобразование отработанных шин в энергию: обзор процессов пиролиза и производства активированного угля и связанных с ними проблем» / Н.Х. Зерин, М.Г. Расул, М.И. Джахирул, А.С. М. Сайем // Наука об окружающей среде – 2023. Том 905. 166981 с.

© *Atayev Matlab Shichbala, Mirzali Elvin Sardar, 2026*

Поступила в редакцию 09.03.2026

Принята к публикации 26.03.2026

Для цитирования:

Atayev Matlab Shichbala, Mirzali Elvin Sardar Study of the conditions for producing bitumen based on alternative feedstocks and oxidizing agents [Текст] / Atayev Matlab Shichbala, Mirzali Elvin Sardar // Инновационные научные исследования. – 2026. – № 3-1(71). – С. 27-44. – DOI 10.5281/zenodo.20260805.